

Development of modern, automated machinery constructive elements of technological equipment of production

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Annotation: The main basic units of the Digital software controlled machines are high precision, singleness, vibration free made durable, reliable, because they are expensive automated equipment, and it is required to work in two or more shifts a day.

Key words: the Digital software controlled lathes, automating tool, guide, support.

1. Structural elements of the Digital software controlled machines
2. Feedback sensors
3. Stepper motor
4. Automatic tool change devices

The Bed frames. The frames of the Digital software controlled machines are the main base element, because machine guides are placed in them. The following types of rooms occurs.

1) Cast iron bars, rolled and polished steel guides, roller equipped with rolling and hydrostatic guides.

2) Welded bars and columns, in most cases, have rectangular guides, welding and heat treatment in a special technology ensures long-term preservation of the obtained accuracy.

3) the Digital software controlled lathes to ensure the swarf output has a vertical or inclined position of the reference plane.

Referrals.

There are types of Sliding, rolling and combination of guides :

Rolling and combination guides are most common on the Digital software controlled lathes. In such routers, large rolling steel plates are used, plate by plate preloaded roller supports move (rotating roller referrers). Roller supports (they are sometimes called tankettes) , it is installed on the frame using different adjusting devices .

One of the main constructive features of multi-operation stanzas controlled in a digital program is the presence of an automatic instrument switching device in them. In general, a system of devices and mechanisms consisting of two main elements for automating tool replacement: a tool storage magazine, which is enough to handle one or more raw products; an automatic tool replacement device is used to transfer the tool from the magazine to the tin spindle and reverse. To replace them in the axial position of the tools in the magazine housing and barrel spindle, it is enough to rotate the magazine until the magazine housing axis matches the spindle axis, pull the tool out of the magazine and secure it in the spindle. Installation of the tool in the store, on which the work is performed, is carried out in reverse order.

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